

LABOR EFFICIENCY: RESULTS AND ANALYZES**Lobar Anvarova**

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Annotation. The article analyzes the issue of labor productivity and social factors affecting it. Feedback has been expressed on achieving labor efficiency, organizing labor and ensuring economic stability.

Keywords: economy, labor productivity, social factors, goods, money, attitude to work, cost, economic stability.

Currently, in the context of the globalization of the world economy, the development of modern industry is characterized by a high degree of specialization. As a result, the deepening of the social division of Labor manifests itself in the expansion of the formation of most production vapors in the industrial structure. In 2018, the share of the industry in the world GDP was 25.0%, and the contribution of those employed in this sector was 23.0% [1]. Currently, structural changes have occurred in the industrial sector as a result of reforms aimed at modernizing, technical and technological requirement of modern sectors of the economy in our republic.

As a result, the share of the industry of our country in the gross domestic product is regularly growing. In particular, this figure was 26.3 percent as of 2018, compared to 12.9 percent in 2000 [3]. At the same time, in the Republic of Uzbekistan "... further modernization and diversification of the industry by moving high-tech Processing Industries to a qualitatively new level, aimed primarily at the rapid development of high-value-added finished products on the basis of deep processing of local raw materials resources" [2] are among the priorities. Effective solution of these tasks research on scientific and methodological and practical aspects of improving the social and economic efficiency of labor based on the effective use of personal activities in industrial enterprises is relevant. Indicators that reflect macroeconomic stability and economic growth in our republic are a practical expression of the success of the reform strategy, the deepening of economic reforms and the achievements in the priorities of the development of the country. Today, in determining the current and future measures of the socio-economic development of our country, it is necessary to comprehensively take into account the level of development of spheres and sectors and their demand for personnel, to formulate economic

development programs from the point of view of these processes and to implement them consistently.

Therefore, the effective use of Labor, which is considered an important factor in production in industrial enterprises, is an important factor in future strategic development. One of the tools that determines the ways of effective use of personal labor in the conditions of modernizing the economy of our republic is the identification of sources and reserves of increasing labor efficiency. In industrial enterprises, labor efficiency and the indicators that represent it are a synthesis of all indicators in the direction of Labor. Therefore, in sufficient research of the socio-economic nature of the indicator of labor efficiency, it is necessary to carry out a comprehensive analysis of labor indicators that are interconnected. Currently, there is no single approach to the comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness of personal labor in industrial enterprises.

Therefore, the development of a comprehensive (integrated) method of assessment of the effectiveness of personal labor is one of the pressing problems. When developing a methodology for complex assessment of labor efficiency, it is necessary to pay attention to the criteria and indicators of its identification. In our opinion, achieving high labor results based on the effective use of all material and labor resources is the main criterion for increasing labor efficiency. The purpose of the study is to develop scientifically based proposals and recommendations for improving the socio-economic mechanism for improving the effectiveness of personal activities in regional industrial enterprises in the conditions of modernization of the economy. Methodological foundations and methods of research. Methodological foundations of scientific and practical research are the laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decrees and decisions of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, references of the Ministry of Economy and Industry, State Statistics Committee and other relevant regulatory legal acts.

The study used systematic analysis, comparative analysis, macroeconomic analysis, grouping, experiment, decomposition, Adaptive Methods, innovative and integrational approaches, analysis and aprobasia of indicators representing labor efficiency in territorial industrial enterprises on the basis of international experiments. Analysis and results. In the analysis of labor efficiency in production enterprises, it is important to express its relationship with the indicator of productivity, since labor productivity is a quantitative indicator that represents labor efficiency. When calculating the indicators necessary for the analysis of labor productivity, the following are used: Gross Value Added By

Industry, annual quantitative indicators of those who are engaged in the network.

In the analysis of labor efficiency in production enterprises, it is important to express its relationship with the indicator of productivity, since labor productivity is a quantitative indicator that represents labor efficiency. When calculating the indicators necessary for the analysis of labor productivity, the following are used: Gross Value Added By Industry, annual quantitative indicators of those who are engaged in the network. When comparing labor productivity at the level of industries, the amount of Gross Value Added created in the network is determined by the ratio of the number of people employed in the Network:, (1) where: W is the level of labor productivity in the network – industrial network; Y_{QQ} is the gross value created in the industrial network; N is the number of people. The application of such a method of calculating labor productivity in industrial production networks is expressed through the following factors. First, the application of natural indicators in several types in the production process of industrial enterprises complicates the calculation of productivity. Secondly, according to the principles of the system of national accounts in our country, the absence of certain connections between indicators such as labor costs and production volumes for statistical accounts, such connections between social and economic indicators can be observed in limited networks of the sphere of material production. In the main branches of industry, gross value added is determined by spending for the value of Labor, the ratio between value (gross value added) and labor costs (labor value) is close to 1 unit (value added = cost of work cost + profit. 1 unit if there is no profit). Therefore, often the efficiency indicator is close to zero. In some cases it can also be below zero. Accordingly, statistics of employed people (number of workers) on networks are used to assess labor productivity. Thirdly, it is advisable to carry out the statistics within the presented network through a single methodological basis for comparison with the statistical indicators of other sectors of the economy, as well as on a single statistical assessment. In this case, the average number of manufactured products, developers, different levels of the value of the main production funds and different network indicators are formed. Since the gross value added (Y_{AQQ}) indicator is a Value Indicator in the processing industry sectors, we used the deflator (comparison) method, that is, to make the gross value added amount appear comparable. To compare value indicators, we use the following deflators (comparable indices). That is, to analyze the effectiveness of the activities of the processing industries in the

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Jizzakh region, comparative indicators were selected that represent the results of the production activities of the food industry, textile industry and metallurgical industry in 2014-2018. Analysis shows that gross value added (YQQ) volume in the processing industry sectors being analyzed in the province has a trend of regular growth in 2014-2018. In 2014-2018, the growth rate of yqq has increased to 2.9 times in the food industry and 2.4 times in the textile industry. And in the metallurgical industry increased by 11.5 times. At the same time, employment in the sectors of this processing industry of the region also has a tendency to grow regularly [4].

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